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OF EDUCATION IN THE FACE OF
INSECURITY IN NIGERIA**

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LOC, Chairman
Prof. Bashir Suleiman
bashirsuleiman@fugusau.edu.ng

LOC, Secretary
Dr. Yakubu A. Abdullahi
abdullahiyakub@fugusau.edu.ng